

Effects of ASEI-PDSI Approach on Self-Efficacy in Chemistry among Secondary School Students in Ilorin Educational Zone, Kwara State

Muhammed, Ashiat Bolanle Ph.D.

Email: bolaashiat@gmail.com

Tel: +2348034676566

Department of Science Education, University of Ilorin, Nigeria

Abstract

Studies have consistently reported that students' self-efficacy is congruent to their achievement in chemistry, and that innovative instructional approaches promote self-efficacy. The Activity, Student-centered, Experiment, Improvisation-Plan, Do, See, improve (ASEI-PDSI) approach is a pedagogical model for strengthening mathematics and science education in Nigeria and thought to promote high self-efficacy among students. Hence, this study investigated the effects of ASEI-PDSI approach on Senior School students' self-efficacy in chemistry. The study adopted a quasi-experimental, non-randomized, pretest, posttest, control group design. The population was all the 40,379 Senior School students offering chemistry in Ilorin, Nigeria during the 2021/2022 academic session, while the target population was 13,460 Senior School I (SSI) students offering chemistry. The sample comprised 292 SSI (138 males and 154 females) students from four randomly selected co-educational schools in Ilorin, Nigeria. The ASEI-Instructional Package (ASEI-IP) was the stimulus instrument while the Chemistry Self-efficacy Scale (CSES) was the test instruments. The reliability of CSES was found to be 0.78. The data gathered were analysed using Analysis of Covariance and t-test statistics. The finding of the study revealed that there was a significant difference in the self-efficacy of students exposed to ASEI-PDSI approach (experimental) and those not exposed (control). The study concluded that ASEI-PDSI approach promote self-efficacy among students and ASEI-PDSI approach should be adopted by teachers to teach chemistry.

Keywords: ASEI-PDSI, Chemistry, Senior School Students, SMASE, Self-efficacy

Introduction

The Nigerian government through the Federal Ministry of Education (FME) saw the need to put innovations in education to practice. Thus, adopted the Strengthening Mathematics and Science Education (SMASE) in-service training and encouraged teachers to teach science and mathematics with ASEI-PDSI approach. The ASEI is an acronym for Activity, Student-centered, Experiment and Improvisation, an inherent strategy that promotes student-centered pedagogy among teachers while PDSI stands for Plan, Do, See, and improve that encourages culture of teachers' continuous improvement (Mwelese & Atwoto, 2014). The SMASE Nigeria project provides a forum for mathematics, biology, chemistry, and physics teachers across the country to gain new ideas, revise their knowledge on content matter, pedagogical issues and resource utilization through the ASEI-PDSI. The principle of ASEI-PDSI approach serves as a foundation upon which teachers can build a substantive and sustainable change in classroom practices with ultimate goal of enhancing the quality of teaching and learning of science and mathematics (SMASE, 2010). Thus, the ASEI-PDSI focused on student-centered, self-discovery learning with little or no facilitation, and reflective thinking.

Studies have consistently reported significant improvement in achievement when students are exposed to ASEI-PDSI approach (Kaman, Wilson, & Thinguri, 2014; Mwelese & Awoto, 2014; Kiige & Atina, 2016; Adamu, 2017; Protus et al., 2020). Besides these cognitive benefits, the students' affective domain should not be undermined. Although, improving students' achievement remains the focus of researches in science education, academic success encompasses enhanced achievement and positive psychological conditions. Affective factors such as self-efficacy, attitude, efforts, motivation, and anxiety are important outcomes of learning that also require fierce consideration. Of all these factors, self-efficacy is recognized as the most crucial affect-based learning outcomes (Huang, 2022).

Bandura, (1997) in Karin (2023) viewed Self-efficacy, as the confidence people have in their abilities to excel in a given task. Any individual that possesses a reasonable degree of self-efficacy is likely to attempt challenging task, and exert more effort while performing the task. Thus, when he/she succeeds, he/she credits his/her abilities (Karin, 2023). Self-efficacy, like achievement, should also be viewed as an outcome rather than influence since literature is replete with evidence that individuals' beliefs about their capacities is closely related to their achievement (Fernando, Lawra & Amparo, 2017). That is, the thought that people hold about themselves are double edged sword, they either enhance or hinder their progress (Koura &

Effects of ASEI-PDSI Approach ... (Muhammed, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10114215>

Al-Hebaishi, 2014). Similarly, Bandura, (1997) in Karin (2023) posited that there are assumptions that four factors are responsible for self-efficacy, which are: verbal persuasion; secondary experience; enactive mastery experience; and physiological and emotional states (Bandura, 1997). These factors contribute to self-esteem. Thus, self-efficacy may predict intellectual achievement better than skills alone. Also, past achievement raises self-efficacy, and students' interpretation of past successes and failures may be responsible for subsequent success (Ferrell & Barbera, 2015). Hence, self-efficacy predicts future achievement better than past performance.

Undoubtedly, gender as an important factor interacting with students' self-efficacy cannot be overlooked, especially with increasing emphasis on how to boost man power for technological development as well as increasing the population of females in the field of science and technology. The issue of gender differences in researches in science education is inconclusive. For instance, Louis and Mistele (2012); Kiran and Sungur (2012) reported no significant gender difference in students' self-efficacy while Huang (2013), Namaziandost and Cakmak (2020) noted that female had higher self-efficacy than their male counterparts in science subjects. There is no doubt that the knowledge of chemistry is germane to national and technological advancement. However, its teaching/learning is confronted with challenges of students' under-achievement and several affective factors, low self-efficacy inclusive. Factors, such as inappropriate teaching methods, poor classroom organization by teachers, lack of motivation and so on may be responsible for these. Although, studies have consistently reported that students' self-efficacy is intertwined with achievement in science with considerable evidence available to support direct effects of self-efficacy on science achievement (Kapucu, 2017; Davila-Acedo et al, 2022), in the past, little effort, if not any has been done in answering the question, "what can be done to promote self-efficacy among students"? However, in recent times, efforts are being made by researchers in science education to promote self-efficacy by advocating for use of innovative instructional strategies. This is evident in the studies of Rachmah, 2017; Davila-Acedo et al, 2022; Gungor et al, 2022; Huang, 2022 that explored the effects of jigsaw cooperative learning; active learning methodology; virtual reality; head-mounted display virtual reality respectively on students' self-efficacy. These studies reported significant improvement in students' self-efficacy and thus, enhanced achievement.

Having established that students' self-efficacy is congruent to their achievement, and that innovative instructional strategies promote self-efficacy, the ASEI-PDSI approach could also be used to promote students' self-efficacy. Studies on ASEI-PDSI approach have always focused on promoting students' and teachers' positive attitudinal change towards teaching and learning of science; and ultimately, improving students' achievement in science and mathematics (Ambasa et al., 2019; Kiige & Atina, 2016; Ayeigo et al., 2015; Barasa, 2015). In essence, examining the effects of ASEI-PDSI approach on self-efficacy should also be explored since the overall goal is to enhance achievement.

It is therefore, a focus in this study to contribute to literature by exploring the influence of gender on students' self-efficacy in chemistry. The overall aim of this research was to examine the effects of ASEI-PDSI instructional approach on senior school students' self-efficacy in chemistry.

Objectives of the study

This study examined the effects of the use of ASEI-PDSI approach on students' self-efficacy in chemistry in Ilorin, Nigeria. Specifically, the study found out:

1. the difference in the self-efficacy of students exposed to ASEI-PDSI instructional strategy and those not exposed to ASEI-PDSI instructional strategy; and
2. the difference in the self-efficacy of male and female students exposed to ASEI-PDSI approach.

Research Questions

To guide the present study, the following research questions were raised to address the objectives of the research:

1. What is the effect of ASEI-PDSI approach on students' self-efficacy in chemistry?
2. What is the difference in self-efficacy of students exposed to ASEI-PDSI approach based on gender?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance in this study

1. There is no significant difference in the self-efficacy of students exposed to ASEI-PDSI and those not exposed to ASEI-PDSI approach.
2. There is no significant difference in the self- efficacy of male and female students exposed to ASEI-PDSI approach.

Effects of ASEI-PDSI Approach ... (Muhammed, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10114215>

Methodology

The study adopted 2 x 2 quasi-experimental research design involving pretest, posttest, non-randomized control groups. The first 2 represents the experimental and the control groups; the next 2 represents the students' gender, also at two levels of male and female. Also, in this study, intact classes of the students were involved so as to avoid distortion of the regular school program and to control for selection bias. The experimental and control groups were exposed to pre-self-efficacy test and the corresponding post-self-efficacy test. The population was all the 40,379 Senior School students offering chemistry in Ilorin, Nigeria during the 2021/2022 academic session; while the target population was all first year Senior School students (SSI) offering chemistry in Ilorin. The choice of SSI as the target population was based on the fact that SSI is the introductory class to chemistry as a subject, as such, it is essential to advocate for high self-efficacy among the students at this early stage. As at the time of the study, there were seventy-eight (78) public Senior Schools in Ilorin, Nigeria. Out of these 78 schools, seven (7) schools are not co-educational, thus, they were exempted from the study. Four (4) schools with qualified chemistry teachers which have been presenting candidates for Senior School Certificate Examinations (SSCE) for at least ten years, and not situated close to one another were selected from the remaining 71 schools in Ilorin using simple random sampling technique. The sampled schools were randomized into experimental and control groups and their intact classes were involved in this study with a total sample size of 292 students (138 males and 154 females).

Two instruments were used in gathering data in this study: the ASEI Instructional Package (ASEI-IP); the Chemistry Self-Efficacy Scale, (CSES). The ASEI Instructional Package (ASEI-IP) was a stimulus instrument that is made up ASEI activity sheet, the ASEI lesson plan, ASEI interaction plan, and ASEI chalkboard plan for the experimental group. The ASEI activity sheet provided the students with step-by-step procedures to employ during instruction; while the ASEI lesson plan is a plan on acids, bases and salts. The content of acids, bases and salts was considered appropriate because of its interwoven link with everyday phenomena and other chemistry concepts. Also, acid-base chemistry is a fundamental concept in chemistry that covers primary, secondary, pre-service education and postgraduate education. The ASEI lesson plan showed the intended lesson objectives, procedures in achieving the stated objectives through relevant class activities, linkage of the prior knowledge to the concept of acids, bases and salts, linkage of activities to acids, bases and salts through posing key questions, and content organization from simple to complex. The ASEI interaction plan contained the types of questions to be asked by the teacher, the expected responses from the students and the questioning techniques at each stage of the lesson. The ASEI chalkboard plan showed the logical flow of the lesson, corresponding to each step of the lesson plan.

The Chemistry Self-Efficacy Scale, (CSES) consisted ten (10) statements on students perceived self-efficacy on acids, bases and salts with responses on a 4-point Likert ranging from strongly agree (4) to strongly disagree (1). The scores from the CSES ranged from the lowest, 10 (25%) to the highest, 40 (100%) and any score below 62.5% were considered to possess low self-efficacy. The CSES was the modified version of the college chemistry self-efficacy scale (CCSES) of Uzuntiryaki and Aydin (2009). The CCSES was used to measure students' self-efficacy on chemistry as whole. However, the CSES in this study measured students perceived self-efficacy on acids, bases and salts only. Other modifications made include changing the response modes from very poorly, poorly, well, and very well to strongly disagree, disagree, agree and strongly agree respectively in the belief that the response modes better represent respondents' personal opinions. This change was also necessitated due to transformation of items in the CCSES from questions to statements. The instruments were given to two experts in Department of Science Education, University of Ilorin, Nigeria; two experienced Senior School chemistry teachers; a senior lecturer in the Department of Chemistry, University of Ilorin for both face and content validity. This ensured that these instruments were appropriate and the items measured what they were designed to measure. Also, in order to ascertain the internal consistency, the CSES was trial tested. A test-retest reliability method was employed involving 20 non-participating SSI students in Ilorin with an interval of two weeks between the first and the second test. The resulting data were analyzed using Cronbach's alpha. The reliability coefficients of CSES was found to be 0.78. Hence, the CSES was adjudged to be reliable.

A letter of introduction was presented to the principals of the sampled schools. This was to seek their permissions and consents to involve their schools, teachers and allow their students to take part in the study. The researcher interacted with the chemistry teachers, enlightened and acquainted them with the nature of the study and thus, formally sought their consents through the informed consent forms, to serve as research assistants for this study. Also, the researcher met with the students and apprised them of the significance and benefits of the study to their academic pursuits. Similarly, the researcher affirmed and disclosed to the students that: the data obtained from the study is strictly for research purpose; their identity would be treated with utmost confidentiality; the study would not be forced on them; and they may withdraw their participation at any stage of the study. Hence, the consents of the students and that of their parents were sought through filling of the informed

Effects of ASEI-PDSI Approach ... (Muhammed, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10114215>

consent forms. The researcher revisited the sampled schools to retrieve the informed consent forms and ascertained the participation status of the subjects of the study. The research assistants for the experimental group received a special training on how to use ASEI-IP and were provided with training manual for reference purpose. The experimental group was taught with ASEI-IP while the control group was taught without using ASEI-IP. The CSES was administered as pre-treatment self-efficacy test to both groups to measure their self-efficacy prior to the treatment. Six periods of forty minutes lesson were used in each of the schools for the actual treatments. The control group was taught using the conventional method of teaching. However, the students in the experimental group worked cooperatively in a group of seven, where each member of a group had specific task assigned and interacted with the materials provided, and the ASEI-activity sheet served as guide to reaching the lesson objectives. The researcher and the research assistants only facilitated the learning process in this group. Thereafter, the CSES was administered post self-efficacy test after the treatment.

Results

Table 1: Demographic Data of the Subjects

Group		Gender		Total
		Male	Female	
Experimental	F	83	70	153
	%	54.2	45.8	100
Control	F	55	84	139
	%	39.6	60.4	100
Total	F	138	154	292
	%	47.3	52.7	100

As shown in Table 1, there are 292 valid subjects with total of 138 male and 154 female participants in both groups. The experimental group exposed to ASEI-PDSI approach comprised 153 (83 males, 70 females) subjects while control group that was not exposed to ASEI-PDSI comprised 139 (55 males, 84 females) subjects.

Research Question 1:

What is the effect of ASEI-PDSI approach on students' self-efficacy in chemistry?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Self-Efficacy Test by Groups

Groups	N	Tests	Mean	Std. Deviation	Remark
Control	139	Pre-test	26.37	6.22	Fair
		Posttest	25.79	5.92	Fair
Experimental	153	Pre-test	26.23	4.64	Fair
		Posttest	28.68	3.82	Better

Table 2 shows the arithmetic mean of students' posttest scores in the control and experimental groups as $\bar{x}=25.79$ and 28.73 respectively. Hence, a difference of 2.94 in the favour of experimental group was observed. Hence, there was difference in the self-efficacy of students exposed to ASEI-PDSI approach and those not. Consequently, a one-way between-groups analysis of covariance was conducted to find out if the difference was statistically significant using the pre-test as covariate. Preliminary checks were conducted to ensure that there was no violation of assumptions of normality, linearity, homogeneity of variances and reliable measurement of the covariate.

Research Question 2

What is the difference in self-efficacy of students exposed to ASEI-PDSI approach based on gender?

Table 5: Mean and Standard Deviation of Male and Female Students in Post-attitude Test

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Male	83	26.88	4.07	1.14
Female	70	24.77	3.77	1.35

Effects of ASEI-PDSI Approach ... (Muhammed, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10114215>

Table 5 shows the arithmetic mean of \bar{x} = 26.88 and 24.77 in the post self-efficacy test for male and female students in the experimental group respectively after the intervention. A mean difference of 2.11 was noted. Hence, there was difference in the chemistry self-efficacy of male and female students exposed to ASEI-PDSI approach.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the self-efficacy of students exposed to ASEI-PDSI and those not exposed to ASEI-PDSI approach.

Table 3: Analysis of Covariance for Difference between Group Means in Self-Efficacy Test

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	789.86 ^a	2	394.93	18.39	.00	.21
Intercept	1768.83	1	1768.83	82.39	.00	.38
Pre-Self-efficacy	493.61	1	493.61	22.99	.00	.15
Group	328.75	1	328.75	15.31	.00	.10
Error	2919.94	289	21.47			
Total	108197.00	292				
Corrected Total	3709.799	291				

a. R Squared = .213 (Adjusted R Squared = .201)

Table 4

Bonferroni Post-Hoc Test on Students' Self-Efficacy between Groups

(I) Group	(J) Group	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Control	Experimental	-3.097*	.79	.00	-4.66	-1.53
Experimental	Control	3.097*	.79	.00	1.53	4.66

The result of ANCOVA in Table 3 reveals a statistically significant difference at $p < .05$ alpha level in self-efficacy scores for the experimental and control ($F_{(1,289)} = 15.32, p = .00$, partial eta squared = .10). Post hoc comparisons using Bonferroni in Table 4 indicated a Mean score for the experimental group ($\bar{x} = 3.09, p = .00$) was significantly different from control with Mean score ($\bar{x} = 0.79, p = .00$).

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the self- efficacy of male and female students exposed to ASEI-PDSI approach.

Table 6: The t-test Analysis for Difference between Male and Female Students' Mean Scores in Post Self-efficacy Test

Levene's test for Equality of Variance		t-test for Equality of Mean							
F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		
							Lower	Upper	
Equal variances assumed	.34	.56	2.70	151	.01	2.94	1.76	-1.63	5.37

Effects of ASEI-PDSI Approach ... (Muhammed, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10114215>

Consequently, in Table 6, an independent sample t-test was conducted to compare the self-efficacy of male and female students in the treatment group reveals a statistically significant difference in scores for males ($\bar{x} = 26.88$, $SD = 4.07$) and females ($\bar{x} = 24.77$, $SD = 3.77$, $t_{(151)} = 2.70$, $p = .01$, two-tailed).

Discussion of Findings

This study explored the effects of using ASEI-PDSI approach to promote high self-efficacy among senior school students in chemistry. Hence, the main effect of ASEI-PDSI and influence of gender on chemistry self-efficacy were examined. The outcome of this study revealed that a significant difference existed in the self-efficacy of students exposed to ASEI-PDSI approach (experimental) and those not exposed (control), in the positive direction of the experimental group. This implies that the experimental group possessed high self-efficacy in chemistry than their control group counterparts. Perhaps, this could be because the confidence in handling materials was built as a result of sharing resources and ideas, each individual having a specific task assigned and interdependence on one another. This finding agrees statistically with the findings of Davila-Acedo et al. (2022); Gungor et al. (2022); Fitriyana, Niyarsi and Sugiyarto (2018); Rachmah (2017) that better mode of instruction could enhance students' self-efficacy. Conversely, the finding is not consistent with that of Huang, 2022, Mari and Gumel (2015); Abdelraheem (2014). These researchers also believed that when students are engaged in activities, self-efficacy is enhanced which could result in better achievement. Therefore, ASEI-PDSI approach may be used to enhance self-efficacy in chemistry.

The finding on influence of gender on self-efficacy of students exposed to ASEI-PDSI approach suggested a significant difference in self-efficacy of male and female students exposed to the treatment, which was in favour of the males. This implies that the male students possessed high self-efficacy than their female counterparts. The high self-efficacy of the male students could be as a result of the fact that, in most of the groups, the male students assumed the leadership role, were always the first to carry out any activity that involves manipulation of materials and were more favourably disposed to the activities. This finding is coherent statistically with the findings of Ahmad (2012); Fallan and Opstad (2016) that reported that male students possessed high self-efficacy in chemistry than their female counterparts. However, the findings of Sawari and Mansor (2013); Tenaw (2013) contrast the finding of this study as these researchers reported no significant difference in self-efficacy of male and female students. Also, Huang (2013), Namaziandost and Cakmak (2020) reported that female had higher self-efficacy than their male counterparts in science subjects

Conclusion

This article explored the effects of ASEI-PDSI approach on chemistry self-efficacy of senior school students. The result showed that ASEI-PDSI significantly enhanced students' self-efficacy in chemistry. That is, when ASEI-PDSI approach is used to teach chemistry, the students' self-efficacy is magnified. Also, male students possessed high self-efficacy than their female counterparts in ASEI-PDSI classroom. To this end, the following recommendations among others were made: ASEI-PDSI approach should be adopted by teachers to teach chemistry; self-efficacy of students should be monitored periodically to avoid plummet in students' self-efficacy; teachers should always pay attention to the need to promote students' self-efficacy when scheduling their teaching activities taking into consideration the gender differences; the teachers should also be gender conscious when assigning roles to the students during class activities.

References

- Abdelraheem, A. Y. (2014). Enhancing students' learning and self-efficacy through blended learning in a teachers' program. *I-manager's Journal of Educational Technology*, 10(4). Retrieved from <https://www.academia.edu/enhancing>
- Adamu, I. (2017). *Impact of ASEI strategy on mathematics performance of primary six pupils in Zaria Local Government Area of Kaduna State, Nigeria* (Unpublished master's dissertation). Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria. Retrieved from <http://kubanni.abu.edu.ng/jspui/handle/123456789/9875>
- Ahmad, S. (2012). Relationship of academic SE to self-regulated learning, SI, test anxiety, and academic achievement. *International Journal of Education*, 4(1), 12-25. Retrieved from <http://www.macrothink.org/ije>
- Ambasa, N. W. S., Ayere, M., & Rabari, J. (2019). Extent of use of ASEI-PDSI approach in teaching science in primary schools in Inemuhaya Sub-county, Vihiga County, Kenya. *European Journal of Education Studies*, 6(7), 322-344. Retrieved from <https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejes/article/view/2692>

Effects of ASEI-PDSI Approach ... (Muhammed, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10114215>

- Ayeigo, E. M., Mang'are, P. A., Ngome, C. K., & Mandilah, L. (2015). Analytical study of the extent of practice and implementation of ASEI-PDSI approach by teachers of mathematics in Vihiga, County, Kenya. *America Research Journal of Mathematics*, 1(2), 7-19. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/2847220334>
- Barasa, A. N. (2015). *Influence of strengthening mathematics and science education on pupils' science performance in public primary schools in Samia Sub-county, Kenya* (Unpublished master's dissertation). University of Nairobi, Kenya. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/1b7b4f5ff39ba7dc80c60b2107b8045c6d6893af>
- Davila-Acedo, M. A., Sanchez-Martin, J., Airado-Rodriguez, D., & Canada-Canada, F. (2022). Impact of an active learning methodology on students' emotions and self-efficacy beliefs towards the learning of chemical reactions- the case of secondary education students. *Education Sciences*, 12(5). <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci12050347>
- Fallan, L., & Opstad, L. (2016). Students' self-efficacy and gender-personality interactions. *Journal of Higher Education*, 5(3), 32-44. <https://dx.doi.org/10.5430/ijhe.v5n3p32>
- Fernando, D. B., Lawra, A. R., & Amparo, G. A. (2017). Self-efficacy, satisfaction and academic achievement: The mediator role of students' expectancy value beliefs. *Front Psychology*, 8(1193), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2017.01193>
- Ferrell, B., & Barbera, J. (2015). Analysis of students' self-efficacy, interest, and effort beliefs in general chemistry. *Chemistry Education Research & Practice*, 16, 318-317. Retrieved from <http://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/articlelanding/2015/rp/c4rp00152d>
- Fitriana, N., Niyaris, A., & Sugiyarto, D. (2018). The profile of students' self-efficacy on hydro-carbon hybrid learning and android-based-game. *International Journal on New Trends in Education & their Implications*, 9(2). <https://www.researchgate.net/publication>.
- Gungor, A., Kool, D., Lee, M., Avraamidou, L., Eisink, N., Albada, B., Van der Kolk, K., Tromp, M., & Bitter, J. H. (2022). The use of virtual reality in a chemistry lab and its impact on students' self-efficacy, interest, self-concept and laboratory anxiety. *Eurasia journal of mathematics, science and technology education*, 18(3), 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.29333/ejmste/11814>
- Huang, C. (2013). Gender differences in academic self-efficacy: a meta-analysis. *European Journal of Psychology of Education*, 28(1), 1-35. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10212-011-0097-y>
- Huang, W. (2022). Examining the impact of head-mounted display virtual reality on science self-efficacy of high schoolers. *Interactive Learning Environment*, 30(1), 100-112. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2019.1641525>
- Kaman, K. J., Wilson, K., & Thinguri, R. (2014). An evaluation of the effectiveness of SMASSE program in performance of science and mathematics in primary schools in Kenya. *International Journal of Education & Research*, 2(6), 10-20. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/8406a0dd1ec58b9134731746afcf42a5fd3e9f41>
- Kapucu, S. (2017). Predicting physics achievement: attitude towards physics, self-efficacy of learning physics and mathematics achievement. *Asia-Pacific Forum on Science Learning and Teaching*, 18(10), 123-132
- Karin, K. (2023). *Self-efficacy: Helping students believe in themselves*. <https://serc.carleton.edu/20538>
- Kiige, M. J., & Atina, J. O. (2016). The extent to which teachers of mathematics and chemistry have employed use of ASEI and PDSI approaches for SMASSE in schools. *British Journal of Education*, 4(9), 39-45.
- Kiran, D. & Sungur, S. (2012). Middle school students' science self-efficacy and its sources. Examination of gender difference. *Journal of Science Education and Technology*, 21(5), 619-630. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10956-011-9351-y>
- Koura, A. L., & Al-Hebaish, S. M. (2014). The relationship between multiple intelligence, self-efficacy and academic achievement of Saudi gifted and regular intermediate students. *Educational Research International*, 3(1), 48-71.
- Mari, J. S., & Gumel, S. A. (2015). Effects of jigsaw model of cooperative learning on self-efficacy and achievement in chemistry among concrete and formal reasoners in Colleges of Education in Nigeria. *International Journal of Information & Education Technology*, 5(3), 195- 199.
- Mistele, J. M., & Louis, R. A. (2012). The difference in scores and self-efficacy by students' gender in mathematics and science. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 10(5), 1163-1190. <http://doi.org/10.1007/s10763-011-9325-9>
- Mwelese, J. K. & Awoto, J. O. (2014). Influence of ASEI-PDSI approach on students' views and attitude towards mathematics instruction. *Journal of Education & Practice*, 5(24), 146-152.
- Namazandost, E., & Cakmak, F. (2020). An account of EFL learners' self-efficacy and gender in the flipped classroom model. *Education and Information Technologies*, 25, 4041-4055. <http://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-020-10167-7>

Effects of ASEI-PDSI Approach ... (Muhammed, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10114215>

- Protus, W. M., Martin, W., & Shikuku, B. (2020). Influence of SMASSE active learning techniques on students' attitude towards mathematics in secondary schools in Biringo County, Kenya. *European Journal of Education Studies*, 6(11), 279-293. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.3659354
- Rachmah, D. N. (2017). Effects of jigsaw learning method on students' self-efficacy and motivation learn. *Journal of Educational Health and Community Psychology*, 6(3), 1-9. <https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as-sdt=0%2C5&q>
- Sawari, S. S., & Mansor, N. (2013). A study of students' general self-efficacy related to gender differences *International Journal of Informative & Futuristic Research*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication>
- Strengthening Mathematics and Science Education (2010). *Handouts for in-service education and training in Nigeria* (Unpublished manuscript). National Teachers' Institute, Kaduna.
- Uzuntiryaki, E. & Aydin, Y. C. (2009). Development and validation of chemistry self-efficacy scale for college students. *Research in Science Education*, 39(4), 539-551.